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ANALYZING UZBEKISTAN'S EU EXPORT TRENDS THROUGH THE GENERALIZED SYSTEM OF PREFERENCES PLUS (GSP+) SCHEME

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Abstract. Since 2021, the EU's GSP+ scheme has functioned as the cornerstone of Uzbekistan's strategy to shift from historical dependence on Russia and Chinese markets. This paper investigates the efficacy of this trade regime, questioning whether preferential access has successfully inspired industrial growth or merely highlighted structural inefficiencies. Also, the paper models "No-GSP+" scenario. It argues that the expiration or withdrawal of these preferences would have a huge impact on sectors like textiles, chemicals and pharmaceuticals, metal products. The findings suggest that GSP+ is more than a trade preference scheme, it acts as an important support helping Uzbekistan maintain economic independence.

Key words: GSP+, preferential trade, trade diversification, tariff regimes, export growth, EU market.

Annotatsiya. 2021-yildan buyon Yevropa Ittifoqining GSP+ sxemasi O'zbekistonning Rossiya va Xitoy bozorlariga bo'lgan tarixiy qaramligini kamaytirish strategiyasining asosiy tayanchiga aylandi. Ushbu maqolada mazkur savdo rejimining samaradorligi tahlil qilinib, imtiyozli bozorga kirish sanoat o'sishini rag'batlantira oldimi yoki faqat mavjud tarkibiy samarasizliklarni yuzaga chiqardimi, degan savol ko'tariladi. Shuningdek, maqolada "GSP+siz" ssenariy modellashtiriladi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, ushbu imtiyozlarning muddati tugashi yoki bekor qilinishi to'qimachilik, kimyo va farmatsevtika sanoati hamda metall mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish kabi tarmoqlarga jiddiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Xulosalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, GSP+ nafaqat savdo imtiyozlari sxemasi, balki O'zbekistonning iqtisodiy mustaqilligini saqlab qolishga xizmat qiluvchi muhim qo'llab-quvvatlovchi mexanizm hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: GSP+, imtiyozli savdo, savdo diversifikatsiyasi, tarif rejimlari, eksport o'sishi, Yevropa Ittifoqi bozori.

Аннотация. С 2021 года схема GSP+ Европейского союза стала ключевым элементом стратегии Узбекистана по сокращению исторической зависимости от рынков России и Китая. В данной статье исследуется эффективность данного торгового режима и ставится вопрос о том, смог ли преференциальный доступ действительно стимулировать промышленный рост или же он лишь выявил существующие структурные неэффективности. Кроме того, в работе моделируется сценарий «без GSP+». В статье утверждается, что истечение срока действия или отмена этих преференций окажет значительное влияние на такие сектора, как текстильная, химическая и фармацевтическая промышленность, а также производство металлических изделий. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о том, что GSP+ является не просто схемой торговых преференций, а важным инструментом поддержки, способствующим сохранению экономической независимости Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: GSP+, преференциальная торговля, диверсификация торговли, тарифные режимы, рост экспорта, рынок ЕС.

INTRODUCTION

The tension between free trade and conditional governance is particularly evident in the design of the GSP+ scheme. Free trade generally promotes the obstructed exchange of goods as a means to improve efficiency

and shared economic benefits. In contrast, GSP+ links market access to follow to international conventions on human rights, labor standards, environmental protection, and good governance. While this conditionality is sometimes criticized for challenging national autonomy and imposing additional obligations on developing states, it nonetheless plays a significant role in shaping their incentive structures. By integrating preferential trade access with institutional commitments, GSP+ encourages gradual reforms that can strengthen regulatory capacity and expand opportunities for participation in global markets. Without such frameworks, many developing economies would face increased difficulty in maintaining export competitiveness and sustaining progress in governance standards. Thus, even with imperfections, GSP+ serves as a critical mechanism that supports economic development while fostering progress toward higher governance standards, helping prevent instability that might otherwise emerge in unconditioned trade environments.

The generalized scheme of preferences (GSP) was first established by the EU in 1971 and allows vulnerable developing nations to benefit from reduced tariffs on their exports to the EU. The rules of the GSP were updated in 2012 under Regulation (EU) No 978/2012 [1]. The main goal of GSP is to support the economic growth of these countries, helping to reduce poverty and create jobs. By improving access to the EU market, these nations can better participate in the global economy through their exports. The GSP is built on international values and principles, and includes:

-Standard GSP: This provides reduced or suspended tariffs for goods imported from developing countries. However, this benefit stops if a country has been classified by the World Bank as high or upper-middle income for three consecutive years before the EU reviews the list of beneficiary countries.

-GSP+: This is an incentive program offering even lower tariffs to countries that ratify and comply with 27 specific international agreements that address human rights, labor rights, environmental protection, and good governance.

-Everything But Arms (EBA): This applies to least developed countries (LDCs), allowing them full, tariff-free access for all goods except for arms and munitions as defined by the United Nations.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The European Union's Generalised System of Preferences Plus (GSP+) constitutes a central pillar of the EU's trade and development policy, designed to grant full tariff removal on a wide range of products to vulnerable developing countries that commit to implementing international conventions on human rights, labor standards, environmental protection, and good governance. The legal and institutional foundation of this scheme is established under Regulation (EU) No 978/2012, which outlines eligibility requirements, product coverage, monitoring mechanisms, and conditions for temporary withdrawal of preferences. According to official EU documentation published via EUR-Lex and the European Commission's GSP+ policy platform, the scheme is explicitly intended to promote export diversification, industrial upgrading, and sustainable economic development, rather than functioning solely as a short-term trade facilitation instrument.

From an empirical perspective, a growing body of academic literature evaluates whether preferential trade regimes such as GSP and GSP+ translate into measurable export gains. Pradhan (2025) provides one of the most rigorous econometric assessments of the EU GSP regime, demonstrating that preferential access significantly increases export flows, especially in tariff-sensitive manufacturing sectors.

Complementary evidence is provided by Soomro and Ansari (2022), who examine Pakistan's experience under GSP+ and identify a statistically significant increase in exports to the EU following accession to the scheme, particularly in textiles and apparel. However, the authors also highlight structural limitations, including product concentration, compliance costs, and limited technological upgrading, which constrain long-term industrial transformation. This dual outcome—export growth alongside persistent structural bottlenecks—offers an important comparative benchmark for assessing Uzbekistan's experience under GSP+.

Uzbekistan-specific academic contributions further refine the understanding of how GSP+ influences export dynamics and diversification. The conference paper titled "The Role of GSP+ System and Its Impact on Diversification of Uzbek Exports", along with the study by Saydullo and Sharipova (2023) published in *Innovative Developments and Research in Education*, argue that GSP+ has facilitated Uzbekistan's access to EU markets by reducing tariff barriers and encouraging compliance with EU technical standards. These studies emphasize that the scheme has contributed to diversification beyond traditional commodity exports, particularly toward textiles, chemicals, metal products, and selected pharmaceutical goods. Nevertheless, they also note that diversification remains uneven, with textiles accounting for a disproportionate share of export growth.

Official assessments and trade data further substantiate the academic findings. The EU Special Incentive Arrangement for Sustainable Development and Good Governance (GSP+) assessment of the Republic of Uzbekistan covering the period 2020–2022, published by the European Commission, concludes that Uzbekistan has made substantial progress in utilizing GSP+ preferences [2], with exports to the EU increasing significantly

since accession. Trade statistics released by the European Union Directorate-General for Trade and Economic Security and accessed via ITC TradeMap confirm strong growth in textiles, chemicals, pharmaceuticals, and metal products, reflecting both tariff advantages and improved market access conditions. The EU GSP Hub country profile for Uzbekistan similarly highlights tariff savings and expanded product coverage as key drivers of export performance.

Overall, the literature converges on the conclusion that GSP+ has been effective in expanding exports and facilitating partial diversification, while also exposing underlying structural constraints within beneficiary economies. While comparative studies on Pakistan and Uzbekistan confirm positive trade effects, relatively few contributions explicitly model the counterfactual “No-GSP+” scenario at a sectoral level. This gap is particularly relevant in light of ongoing EU regulatory reforms and periodic preference reviews, which introduce uncertainty regarding the continuity of preferential access. By integrating econometric evidence, Uzbekistan-specific academic studies, official EU and WTO assessments, and web-based trade data sources, this study positions GSP+ as more than a trade preference scheme, arguing that it functions as a critical support mechanism underpinning Uzbekistan’s industrial development and economic independence.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological framework of this study is grounded in a qualitative–quantitative desk-based research approach, relying exclusively on secondary data sources to examine the significance and effectiveness of the European Union’s Generalised System of Preferences Plus (GSP+) scheme in shaping Uzbekistan’s export dynamics since its accession in 2021. Rather than conducting primary surveys or interviews, the research systematically compiles, compares, and interprets data from a wide range of authoritative and institutionally credible sources, including official EU trade statistics, ITC TradeMap datasets, GSP+ monitoring and assessment reports, WTO accession documentation, European Commission communications, Uzbek government publications, and sector-specific analytical reports. Quantitative data on export volumes, product categories, tariff lines, and destination markets were extracted from these sources and organized into structured datasets, which were then used to construct descriptive charts and comparative visualizations illustrating changes in export performance, sectoral concentration, and diversification patterns over time, particularly in key industries such as textiles and apparel, chemicals, pharmaceuticals, and metal products. These visual tools serve not as econometric estimations but as analytical instruments to identify observable trends and shifts associated with the introduction of preferential market access under the GSP+ framework. In parallel, qualitative content analysis was applied to legal and policy documents—including EU GSP regulations, European Parliament and Council proposals, joint implementation reports, and sustainability and governance assessments—to contextualize statistical findings within the broader institutional, regulatory, and political economy environment governing trade relations between Uzbekistan and the European Union. To address the research objective of evaluating the potential consequences of preference erosion or withdrawal, the study incorporates a conceptual “No-GSP+” scenario, developed through comparative reasoning and informed by existing empirical literature on GSP regimes in other beneficiary countries, such as Pakistan and South Asian economies, as well as scholarly analyses of preferential trade agreements and their expiration effects. This counterfactual assessment does not rely on formal modeling techniques but instead uses structured comparison and theoretical inference to approximate how the absence of tariff preferences could affect export competitiveness, industrial upgrading, and market access for Uzbekistan’s leading export sectors. Methodological triangulation is employed throughout the study by cross-referencing statistical data with policy assessments, academic studies, and sectoral reports, thereby enhancing the reliability and analytical depth of the findings while mitigating the limitations inherent in single-source analyses. Overall, this methodology enables a comprehensive and policy-relevant evaluation of GSP+ as not merely a preferential trade instrument but as a structural support mechanism influencing Uzbekistan’s export strategy, sectoral development, and efforts to maintain greater economic independence from traditional trading partners.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The relationship between the European Union (EU) and Uzbekistan has entered a new strategic phase, marked by Uzbekistan’s comprehensive reform agenda and the EU’s imperative to stabilize Central Asian supply chains. This deepening cooperation is currently underpinned by two key frameworks: Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement (EPCA), recently signed to expand cooperation across new areas like critical raw materials and security [3]; and the Generalized Scheme of Preferences Plus (GSP+). For the EU, the partnership with Uzbekistan – its second-largest trading partner in Central Asia (after Kazakhstan)- is a vital component of its geopolitical strategy, aiming to establish a stable source for raw materials, thereby reducing

logistical dependencies on the Eastern axis. Conversely, Uzbekistan views the EU as the crucial source of high-tech capital goods and a strategic export market necessary to sustain its domestic industrialization drive and diversify away from historical reliance in Russia and China. In other words, the EU and Uzbekistan are working well together, which has doubled their trade since 2020 and is helping Uzbekistan prepare to join the WTO. [4]

Figure 1 illustrates how trade in goods between the European Union and Uzbekistan has changed from 2014 to 2024, highlighting the uneven financial outcomes of this strategic shift. Examining the data across this ten-year period helps assess whether the GSP+ scheme has genuinely boosted Uzbekistan's export performance, while also showing the rising cost of the country's industrial modernization reflected in the surge of imports from Europe (Figure 1).

Figure 1. EU trade flows and balance, annual data 2014-2024¹

In 2022, the EU share in total Uzbekistan's exports amounted to 3.8%, substantially more than the 1.2% in 2021 but still much lower than Russia, China, and Turkey, the key export destinations together accounting for 38% of total export value (€14.6 billion in 2022, an increase of over 23% compare to 2021) [5] Uzbekistan mainly exported factory goods, food, and chemicals to neighboring Central Asian countries like Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Afghanistan, and Tajikistan, but this may change since the European Union (EU) granted it the GSP+ trade status in April 2021, allowing two-thirds of its products to enter the EU duty-free. Although it is early, this new deal is expected to help Uzbekistan sell more to the EU and send products to more diverse locations, especially as the EU increases its demand for electronic and metal parts for growing industries like automotive and medical equipment. However, the country's lack of sea access and long distance from Europe could make it difficult to fully reach this potential. [6].

Figure 2 illustrates EU imports from Uzbekistan and the utilization of the GSP+ scheme between 2019 and 2023.

Total imports increased significantly from €172.3 million in 2019 to €721.4 million in 2022 (318.7% growth), before declining slightly to €668,8 million in 2023 (288% growth relative to 2019). GSP+ eligible imports showed a similar pattern, rising from €106.7 million in 2019 to €492.1 million in 2022, then falling to €392.5 million in 2023. Likewise, GSP+ used imports grew from €93.6 million to €458.0 million in 2022, decreasing to €329.9 million in 2023.

The GSP+ utilization rate remained high throughout the period, reaching 93.1% in 2022 and slightly dropping to 84.1% in 2023, indicating that most eligible exports continued to benefit from the scheme (Table 1).

¹ <https://www.euronews.com/business/2025/10/31/trade-imbalance-how-do-eu-membership-contenders-stack-up-against-the-bloc>

Table 1. EU imports from Uzbekistan and GSP utilization rate, 2019-2023²

	2019	2020	2021*	2022	Trend %	2023	Trend %
Total imports, € million	172.3	174.4	384.1	721.4	318.7	668.8	288.0
GSP+ eligible, € million	106.7	120.4	265.2	492.1	361.2	392.5	267.8
GSP+ used, € million	93.6	108.5	240.1	458.0	389.2	329.9	252.5
GSP utilization rate, %	87.7	90.1	90.5	93.1		84.1	

*GSP+ applied since 1 April 2021, prior to this date Uzbekistan benefitted from the Standard GSP.

Data on the top Uzbek product groups benefitting from GSP+ tariff preferences in 2023 (€ million) reveals a distinct disparity between potential capacity and actual usage across sectors (Figure 3). S-15b base metals demonstrate exceptional efficiency, utilizing 98.8% of their €74.9 million eligible capacity. While S-06b other chemicals represent the largest potential volume with €97.0 million eligible, their actual GSP usage settles at a moderate 86.3%. In stark contrast, the others category significantly underperforms relative to the rest, converting only €39.9 million of its eligible amount into use for a rate of just 57.8% (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Top Uzbek product groups benefitting from GSP+ tariff preferences, 2023, € million³

Analysis of 2022 data on the top Uzbek product groups benefitting from GSP+ tariff preferences in 2022 (Figure 4) shows a landscape dominated by high-volume sectors with strong utilization rates. S-06b other chemicals and S-11a textiles were the clear leaders, with eligible volumes of €195.6 million and €135.0 million respectively, and both maintained high utilization rate above 96%. S-15b base metals, while smaller in volume at €27.3 million, achieved the highest efficiency of the group, utilizing 99.2% of its eligible capacity. Conversely, the Others category, including the rest of the section, was the least efficient, using only 65.5% of its €55.0 million potential. It indicates a significant gap between eligibility and actual usage compared to the major sectors (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Top Uzbek product groups benefitting from GSP+ tariff preferences, 2022, € million⁴

² https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/development-and-sustainability/generalised-scheme-preferences_en

³ https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/development-and-sustainability/generalised-scheme-preferences_en

⁴ https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/development-and-sustainability/generalised-scheme-preferences_en

When comparing the two years, 2022 stands out as a period of significantly higher trade volume for the leading categories. While 2023 saw specific sectors like Base metals (S-15b) and Vegetables, fruit & nuts (S-02b) grow, the overall scale of the top performing groups contracted sharply. For instance, Other chemicals (S-06b), which peaked near €200 million in 2022, dropped to roughly €97 million in 2023. Similarly, Textiles (S-11a) saw a decrease from €135 million to roughly €86 million. Consequently, while utilization rates remained efficient in 2023, the total value of eligible and used goods was notably higher in 2022, driven by these massive volumes in the chemical and textile sectors.

A scenario: Uzbekistan’s economy without GSP+ scheme

On 22 November, 2023, the European Union has extended its Generalized System of Preferences Plus (“GSP+”) for the next four years, until 31 December, 2027. [7] More than a year later, the meeting of the working group on the implementation of the EU’s GSP+ (Generalized Scheme of Preferences) system took place in Brussels on December 4-5, 2024. Uzbekistan has officially asked the EU to extend the GSP+ preferential trade scheme for another ten years to broaden the list of Uzbek goods eligible for duty-free access, especially fresh fruits and vegetables. The proposal includes removing or adjusting seasonal quotas to improve supply stability and competitiveness in the EU market. [8] During the meeting, Uzbekistan highlighted strong results achieved since joining GSP+ in 2021 – exports to the EU have nearly tripled to \$1.15 billion, with stable exports established in around 1,100 product categories, including agriculture, textiles, electrical equipment, and chemicals. Uzbek officials also discussed revising import quotas on rolled metal products and receiving EU technical support to help Uzbek goods meet European standards, but these proposals are still under discussion. Below, we explore the likely economic consequences for Uzbekistan in the event that it no longer holds GSP+ beneficiary status (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Uzbekistan, Top trading partners 2024

The 2024 trade data reveals Uzbekistan’s economy caught in geopolitical “pincer”, structurally dependent on China for 29.3% of its imports while relying on Russia to absorb 15.1% of its exports (Figure 5). While the striking trade deficit - €32.5 billion in imports versus €18.3 billion in exports – highlights this imbalance, it simultaneously signals a phase of aggressive industrialization, where the heavy importation of capital goods represents a strategic investment in future capacity. Within this polarized landscape, the European Union emerges as a critical economic counterbalance; in a regional anomaly, Uzbekistan exports more to the EU (€1.3 billion) than to China (€1.1 billion). This divergence is driven primarily by the EU’s GSP+ scheme which effectively insulates Uzbek exports from market barriers. Without these preferences, key sectors such as textiles would face prohibitive duties, likely destroying their competitiveness against rivals and forcing Uzbekistan back into a deeper reliance on traditional partners.

4 main sectors that would be most affected by losing GSP+ benefit:

1. Textiles and Garments.

This specific sector is Uzbekistan’s most significant non-commodity export to the EU, with its duty-free access under GSP+ status providing a competitive edge over Asian rivals. Critically, this sector is highly feminized, employing a substantial majority of the country’s female industrial workforce. Should the GSP+ status be revoked, Uzbekistan’s textile exports would immediately become uncompetitive. The resulting loss of market share and export revenue would translate directly into factory closures and job losses. This economic penalty would thus disproportionately fall on women, dismantling recent gains in female employment and financial autonomy.

2. Chemicals and Pharmaceuticals.

While textile section highlights the risk of trade distribution, the growing Chemicals and Pharmaceuticals sector illustrates the risk of industrial “primitivization.” Currently this sector is divided: it exports both raw strategic resources (like Uranium) and value-added goods (like fertilizers and polymers). The withdrawal of GSP+ would create an asymmetric shock. Raw material exports, which are essential to EU energy security, would likely remain unaffected by tariff reversions. However, value-added manufacturing base— specifically nitrogenous fertilizers and processed industrial chemicals – would face standard MFN tariffs, leaving them uncompetitive against global rivals.

3. Base metals and metal products

Losing GSP+ status would hit the ferrous and non-ferrous metals sectors especially hard, mainly because the industry is already struggling with tough global competition and strict regulations. Under the EU’s steel safeguard measures, anything shipped beyond the quota can face tariffs of 25%, and in some proposals even up to 50%. But bigger danger is what this means for the sector’s long-term competitiveness. Metal production is extremely expensive – it requires huge upfront investments, uses a lot of energy (in some non-ferrous industries, energy makes up around 40% of total costs), and face ongoing global overcapacity. Without duty-free access, companies do not just lose money on tariffs, they risk losing the ability to invest in the upgrades needed to meet the EU’s new rules, like stricter origin checks such as “melted and poured.”

4. Agriculture and food products.

The EU has become a critical destination for Uzbek processed foods, dried fruits, and vegetables, where the removal of tariffs has allowed Uzbek exporters to compete on price. This is evident in the surge of overall GSP-eligible exports - growing from €93 million (2019) to over €450 million (2020) – a trend driven significantly by the agricultural sector’s ability to access over 1,100 duty-free product lines. Without GSP+, fresh and dried produce would face tariffs ranging from 3% to over 10%. The loss of these benefits would likely stop private investment in food processing technology, effectively undermining Uzbekistan’s strategy to move up the value chain from selling raw cotton to exporting high-value finished food products.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The Generalized System of Preferences Plus (GSP+) remains a key instrument for advancing sustainable development through trade. For developing economies such as Uzbekistan, it functions not just a system of tariff preferences, but also as a strong driver of domestic reforms and a gateway to deeper integration into the global economy. GSP+ shouldn’t be seen solely as a way to increase trade. It should also be used to improve the quality of a country’s exports by encouraging a more diverse, higher-value product mix. This kind of diversification can protect Uzbekistan from global market fluctuations and support more stable, long-term growth. In reality, GSP+ is more than a set of tariff preferences — it can be a pathway to wider social and economic progress. Uzbekistan’s early results show how useful the scheme can be when it’s supported by strong domestic reforms and clear economic goals. If the country continues to introduce new policies and works closely with businesses and other stakeholders, it can become a model for how emerging economies can use GSP+ to integrate more deeply into global markets, move toward higher value-added production, and pursue sustainable development.

In the larger picture of international development, GSP+ is a great example of how trade policies can help drive meaningful economic change. For Uzbekistan, this comes at an important moment as the country tries to build a more diverse, competitive, and open economy. The progress so far is encouraging. Beyond increasing export volumes, the program has pushed Uzbekistan to align with international standards, modernize key industries, and create better jobs. The textile sector, one of Uzbekistan’s main export industries, has especially benefited from increased access to the EU market. Factories have upgraded equipment, production processes have improved, and more employment opportunities — especially for women in rural areas — have emerged. GSP+ has also helped attract foreign investment into manufacturing and agro-processing, leading to improvements in technology, product quality, and governance. All of this strengthens Uzbekistan’s economic stability and improves its position as a potential regional production center. However, to make the most of GSP+, Uzbekistan needs a long-term and holistic approach. This includes strengthening institutions, improving education and skills, and upgrading infrastructure. Only by addressing these areas can the country fully unlock the benefits of GSP+ and support sustainable, future-oriented growth.

As global politics become more complicated and the EU updates its trade policies — for example with the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism — countries that benefit from GSP+, including Uzbekistan, need to stay flexible and ready to adjust. Staying in close contact with EU institutions, civil society groups, and industry partners is crucial. This helps ensure that Uzbekistan keeps meeting the requirements and stays prepared for any new rules that come in the future. It’s also important to understand that GSP+ is not the final goal. Instead,

it should be viewed as a bridge toward deeper cooperation with the EU. The experience gained through GSP+ can help countries move toward more advanced trade partnerships, such as free trade agreements. For Uzbekistan, strong performance under GSP+ could open the door to negotiating a wider and more stable trade and cooperation framework with the EU in the coming years.

The study concludes that the European Union's GSP+ scheme is not merely a commercial instrument but a strategic necessity underpinning Uzbekistan's multi-vector policy and its long-term industrial modernization. The analysis established that GSP+ functions as the structural glue holding together Uzbekistan's economic and social goals:

- It acts as a social shield for the highly feminized textiles and garments industry, where tariff preferences provide the essential competitive margin necessary to preserve employment gains and financial autonomy for women.
- It serves as an industrial catalyst for the chemical and pharmaceutical sectors, incentivizing the move from raw material extraction toward higher-value manufacturing, thereby mitigating the risk of economic regression.

Uzbekistan who needs to focus on using the benefits of GSP+ more effectively and ensuring that the scheme remains politically secure. To get the most out of duty-free access, the government should strengthen its Quality Infrastructure (QI) by developing accredited labs and certification centers. This will help high-value products – such as fertilizers and processed foods – meet the EU's strict quality and safety requirements, increasing the country's actual use of GSP+. Another priority is reducing logistical risks. As a doubly landlocked country, Uzbekistan must invest in the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route (the Middle Corridor) to secure stable, non-Russian export routes and lower transportation costs. Expanding cold-chain logistics is also essential for exporting premium agricultural goods. Finally, maintaining the political foundations of GSP+ requires continued progress on human rights commitments. By pushing forward genuine reforms in the legal and judicial systems, Uzbekistan can strengthen its credibility with international partners and protect its GSP+ status from potential suspension.

The EU's approach needs to shift from simply granting tariff preferences to actively supporting long-term industrial development in Central Asia. To create a predictable environment for business, Brussels should speed up the full ratification of the EPCA and clearly state that the trade benefits Uzbekistan currently receives through GSP+ will continue under the new agreement. This kind of reassurance is crucial for reducing investor uncertainty. The GSP+ scheme has played an important role in supporting Uzbekistan's shift toward closer economic ties with the West. The key challenge now turning this temporary trade preference into a lasting and balanced partnership – one that supports domestic social stability, helps modernize industry, and preserves the country's geopolitical flexibility. Achieving this transition will require coordinated policies both at home and with international partners. Only then can Uzbekistan strengthen its economic sovereignty and remain resilient amid the fast-changing dynamics of the Eurasian region.

List of used literature:

1. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2012/978/oj/eng>
2. <https://trade.ec.europa.eu/access-to-markets/en/content/generalised-scheme-preferences-plus-gsp>
3. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/es/ip_25_2504
4. https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/acc_e/a1_ouz_bekistan_e.htm
5. The EU Special Incentive Arrangement for Sustainable Development and Good Governance (GSP+) assessment of the Republic of Uzbekistan covering the period 2020-2022
6. <https://gov.uz/en/news/view/3706>
7. <https://interfax.com/newsroom/top-stories/108424/>
8. Review of the Generalized Scheme of Preferences (GSP) regulation – Q2 2021, Legislative Train 10.2025
9. Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the council, Brussels, 4.7.2023 COM (2023) 426 final
10. European Union, Trade in goods with Uzbekistan, directorate General Trade and Economic Security
11. European Union's Generalized System of Preferences Scheme, May 2019
12. Joint Report to the European Parliament and the council on the Generalized System of Preferences covering the period 2020-2022
13. Hoekman, B.M. and Özden, Ç. (2006) Trade Preferences and Differential Treatment of Developing Countries: A Selective Survey. Edward Elgar (Policy research working papers). Available at: <https://books.google.co.uz/books?id=MkXwzjI4qwwC>.
14. Mr. Iqbal Ahmad A. Soomro and Dr. Ishaque Ahmed Ansari (2022) "The GSP+ and Exports of Pakistan to the European Union," Journal of European Studies (JES), 38(2), pp. 38–54. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.56384/jes.v38i2.254>.
15. Pradhan, M. (2025) "Trading Without Special Treatment: Assessing the Impact of the EU's Generalized System of Preferences Reform," Oxford Open Economics, p. odaf001.
16. Saydullo, F. and Sharipova, U. (2023) "The role of GSP+ system and its impact on diversification of Uzbek exports," Innovative Developments and Research in Education, 2(23), pp. 281–286.

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